

TERMS AND TEXTS: THE FUNCTIONALITY OF EDITORIAL-POLYGRAPHIC TERMS

[Svetlana CALARAS](#)

Ph.D. Student

(Academy of Sciences of Republic of Moldova)

Abstract

The editorial-polygraphic text, apparently accessible, due to many words from the common language, is still difficult to decode without the help of an explanatory dictionary. In the fragments presented in this paper we notice the preponderance of the non-specialized lexicon to the detriment of the specialized one. The editorial-polygraphic context creates the premises for the extension of the lexical meaning of the term and the appearance on this basis of a specialized meaning. Due to the context, the term acquires specific lexical nuances and becomes a connotatively designated word. However, for an ordinary reader, the text is quite difficult to understand, to decode, keeping a substantial part of restrictive code, intended for the specialized reader.

Keywords: *text, editorial-polygraphic, specialized, context, functions, functional style, disambiguation*

Rezumat

Textul editorial-poligrafic, aparent accesibil, datorită multor cuvinte din limbajul comun, totuși este greu de decodat fără ajutorul unui dicționar explicativ. În fragmentele prezentate în această lucrare, observăm preponderanța lexicului nespecializat în detrimentul celui specializat. Contextul editorial-poligrafic creează premisele pentru extinderea sensului lexical al termenului și apariția, pe această bază, a unui sens specializat. Datorită contextului, termenul dobândește nuanțe lexicale specifice și devine un cuvânt desemnat conotativ. Totuși, pentru un cititor de rând, textul este destul de greu de înțeles, de decodat, păstrându-se o parte substanțială de cod restrictiv, destinat cititorului specializat.

Cuvinte-cheie: *text, editorial-poligrafic, specializat, context, funcții, stil funcțional, dezambiguizare*

The functionality of terminology is accompanied by the study of modern functions in different texts and situations in the field of professions and professional training, as well as the study of the peculiarities of using these terms in specialized speech. In the light of these ideas, we can deduce that there are texts of three types:

- *Term-generating texts* - texts that set out theories and describe knowledge and activities in specialized fields. Thus, term-generating texts can be publications about new printing methods or new programs in the field of design;
- *Term-using texts* - texts that describe objects and processes that belong to a specific specialized field. Such texts can be publications about books, magazines, etc., related to the publishing activity;

- *Term-setting texts* - texts that set terms, such as specialized dictionaries, textbooks, monographs, ISO, etc.

As a landmark in researching the functionality of the terms, we took the editorial-polygraph text, the publishing house being a branch of culture and production, related to the editing, production and distribution of books, magazines, newspapers and other types of printed materials.

The editorial-polygraphic context creates the premises for the extension of the lexical meaning of the term and the appearance on this basis of a specialized meaning. Due to the context, the term acquires specific lexical nuances and becomes a designated connotative word (connotation is understood as the additional component of the semantic value of the lexical unit, which includes: image, emotionality, evaluation and stylistic marking). Thus, an important condition for receiving the editorial-polygraphic terms is the updating of the connotative meaning of the specialized text in a certain context.

Another reason for the connotation is the level of knowledge of the recipient of the text message. We believe that an insufficient understanding of the meaning of a specialized word is compensated by connotative stratifications in the subconscious of the receiver; while the editorial-polygraphic context does not always contribute to the adequate awareness of the term.

As it is known, the function of the terms is to serve the specialized fields of human activity - science, technology, art, etc. The peculiarity of the editorial-polygraphic term, in this context, is that it fixes the results of the knowledge in the specialized field of the editorial-polygraphic activity.

There is a sphere of operation of terms (books, manuals, professional communication) and a sphere of setting, fixing terms (reference books, dictionaries, regulatory documents). The main function of the terms is to serve the specialized fields of human activity.

The functional sphere of editorial-polygraphic terminology is represented by the *purpose of communication* (depending on the amount of information it contains) - narrative, descriptive, argumentative and informative text, and the *functional style* of the text - fiction (artistic), scientific, journalistic, legal and administrative, etc. In this research we will examine the editorial-polygraphic text from the perspective of functional style. Moreover, we can classify the texts as *strictly specialized* (dictionaries, monographs, documents, course materials, etc.), *semi-specialized* (textbooks, specialized press, etc.) and *non-specialized* (general use press, artistic literature, etc.).

1. Scientific Text

We can mention the semi-specialized text of school textbooks, in which we find mentions about books, types of books. For example, in the 2015 edition of the ABC textbook we find the poem „O carte” by Constantin Dragomir about the book: „O carte aleasă/E ca o casă/Cu multe neamuri,/Păsări pe ramuri” (Buruiană, 2015, p. 108).

The strictly specialized text is the one that is concentrated in dictionaries, glossaries, monographs, course materials, textbooks about using the printing technique. For example, in the course materials "Tehnologii poligrafice - flexografia. Note de curs" we have this kind of strictly specialized text: "Cernelurile radicale au în compoziția lor acrilajați. Acrilajații au efect slab după polimerizare, au miros nesemnificativ, rezistență înaltă la acționări mecanice și termice" (Scobială&Lisnic, 2008, p. 59).

We notice the high degree of specialization of the text and the obvious frequency of editorial-polygraphic terminology. We also note the same high degree of specialization in the user manuals (user guide) of the technique: „Pentru o funcționare optimă a imprimantei, nu utilizați hârtie mai grea de 157 g/m². Hârtia care este prea grea poate produce erori de alimentare, probleme la stivuire, blocaje ale hârtiei, fixare proastă a tonerului, calitate scăzută a imprimării sau uzură mecanică excesivă" (HP Laser..., 2011, p. 22).

However, the technical manuals could also be classified in those intended for the non-specialized user, the ordinary user, and those intended for the user specialized in the publishing-printing field, which is indicated by the type of technique and the degree of specialization of the technical manuals. As for dictionaries, at present there are no recently published dictionaries with editorial-polygraphic terminology (only the one from 1991), but we can access online dictionaries in electronic format, such as imprint.md - "Dictionary of typographic terms" (Broșător...), etc.

2. Publicistic Text

The advertising text is characterized by concise, objective and impersonal statements, when it comes to advertisements, prospectuses, news, chronicles, reports, etc. (informative function), and subjective, personal text, which uses literary language, but also some formulations characteristic of colloquial language, when we refer to press articles, editorials, pamphlets, interviews, etc. (persuasive function).

3. Advert/Commercial

The advertising text (electronic advertisement, radio, TV and cinema commercial, billboard, banner, flyer, leaflet, etc.) places more emphasis on the informativeness and laconicity of the advertisement. There are various models of online advertising: e-mail, banner, text link, advertorial, interstitial (pop-up), etc. E.g.: "Broșător. Cerințe: capacitatea rapidă de studiere, responsabilitate, inițiativă, punctualitate. Responsabilități: lucru în secția de producer; lucru manual la sortarea, înclieirea, ambalarea; alte lucrări manuale sau mecanizate în secția de producere poligrafică; [...]" (Broșător...).

4. News Report

"În Europa, în anul 1445, germanul Johannes Gutenberg a produs o revoluție în tipărirea cărților, inventând tiparul cu litere mobile de plumb, care prezenta avantajul că literele din plumb erau rezistente, se puteau refolosi și, mai ales, reșeza în funcție de text, aveau dimensiuni standard și o perioadă

de realizare incomparabil mai scurtă față de orice procedeu cunoscut până la acel moment [...]”¹.

5. Article

The electronic archive of current publications, representing different press segments, was researched for a period between 2015 and 2018: "Timpul", "Jurnal de Chișinău", "Cuvântul", "Ziarul de Gardă", "Vocea Poporului", etc. E.g. *Timpul*: "Nu peste multă vreme, probabil, mașinăria va fi capabilă să printeze [...]”². "Pe Călin, de meserie inginer de *software*, absolvent al Politehnicii din Timișoara [...]” [*idem*].

6. Editorial

"Cartea este un miracol, o sărbătoare de neuitat, ce-i îndeamnă pe copii spre lectură, spre cunoaștere. Salonul Internațional de Carte pentru Copii și Tineret este evenimentul la care miracolul devine realitate [...]” (Colța, 2012).

Studying the press, we notice the increase, every year, of the number of anglicisms in the articles having as the main topic the editorial-polygraphic field.

7. Literary Text (Artistic)

- Poetry

„Nici n-am dat bine drumul
gândurilor să zboare
Căci deja *matrițele tipografice*
Din sufletul meu
Incepuseră, cu zgomot asurzitor [...]” (Dumitrof, 2002).

- Folktale

"Vine apoi *tipograful*, cel care alege-*culege* litere mari, litere mici, rânduri, pagini întregi - privește-mă și ai să-nțelegi. Iar *tipograful* munca își împarte cu cel care-adună și leagă-mpreună, foaie cu foaie, o carte întreagă: *legătorul* [...]” (Caldararu).

- Parable

„Și a plecat băiatul după maica stăriță. Ea l-a dus la o *tipografie* și l-a băgat *ucenic*; i-a dat ceva mărunțele pentru covrigi, l-a blagoslovit și s-a dus [...]” (Caragiale, 1892).

- Novel

"Școala și *cartea* sunt puntea care îți permit să treci de la ignoranță la cunoaștere, la certitudine. Pentru că a ieși din sfera necunoașterii și a întunericului nu este suficient să aprinzi veioza [...]” (Manoli, 2014).

¹Prima carte tipărită în limba română. RadioChișinău.md. 30 ianuarie 2015. <https://radiochisinau.md/prima-carte-tiparita-in-limba-romana-19312>.

²Timpul.md. <https://www.timpul.md/articol/breaking-news---romanii-vor-scoate-organe-la-imprimanta-3d-123131.html>.

- Comics

„În fața sediului gazetei, Simon Bărnăuțiu se întâlnește cu Avram Iancu” (Noran et al., 1988).

8. Legal-administrative Text

Legal-administrative texts are the texts elaborated by the legislative field (articles of law, Constitution, Criminal Code, Labor Code, etc.), texts elaborated by the judicial body, texts elaborated by the administrative body (request, report, certificate, contract, etc.), Norms ISO, etc.

For example, in the Labor Code we have the Labor Protection Norms for the printing industry: „2.5.2. *Hârtie, carton și produse finite*. Art. 107. - Pentru operațiile de *transport, stivuire*, se vor respecta Normele generale de protecție a muncii referitoare la igiena muncii privind efortul fizic” (Hp Laser..., 2011).

In the Constitution we have LAW No. 939 of 20.04.2000 regarding the editorial activity: „Parlamentul adoptă prezenta lege ordinară. Capitolul I. Dispoziții generale. Articolul I. Noțiuni principale. În sensul prezentei legi, se utilizează următoarele noțiuni principale: *autor* – persoana sau colectiv care creează o operă literară, publicistică, științifică sau de alt gen; *beneficiar al producției editoriale* – persoana juridică care comandă producția editorială, asumându-și cheltuielile financiare, etc.” (Scobioală & Lisnic, 2008).

We notice the high degree of specialization of the text, with a high number of editorial-polygraphic terms, a characteristic feature of the scientific text.

Thus, analyzing several types of texts, we came to the conclusion that most editorial-polygraphic terms can be found in semi-specialized texts (manuals, specialized periodicals, monographs, etc.), as well as in the strictly specialized ones (course texts, dictionaries, etc.). Likewise, the correctness of the terms used depends largely on the degree of specialization of the texts.

9. Contextual Disambiguation of Editorial-Polygraphic Terms

As far as we know, the text paradigm is characterized by fixing the meaning of the terms. "Language is by nature ambiguous, and the ultimate principle of disambiguation is recourse to context" (Ungureanu, 2008, p. 347).

The text helps us to distinguish between the paradigmatic and syntagmatic meaning of a linguistic sign. The intrinsic nature of the term is conditioned by the relationship of the text with the sender of the text and, consequently, by the relationship of the text with the recipient of the text. As it was mentioned before, being a linguistic unit, the term is a means of communication and a cognitive element. The term as a means of communication indicates the meaning of communication in terminology, hence the need to study the term in context.

The context creates the premises for extending the lexical meaning of a term and creating a special meaning based on it. Due to the unusual compatibility, hidden meanings appear, the term acquires specific lexical nuances, becomes a designated connotative word (connotation is an

additional component of the meaning of a lexical unit, which includes figurativeness, emotionality, evaluation and stylistic marking). Thus, the first condition for updating the connotative component of the meaning of a term in a text is a context that has a strong generating capacity.

Another cause of the connotation is the level of knowledge of the recipient. We believe that a lack of understanding of the meaning of a particular word is compensated by connotative overlaps; however, the context does not always contribute to the formation of an adequate awareness of the meaning of terms. It should be emphasized that under the influence of the context, respondents often form an incorrect understanding of the meaning of a term.

Often, the contextual disambiguation of terms takes place with the help of specialized text and the more specialized the text (dictionaries, monographs, textbooks, course materials, specialized periodicals, etc.), the clearer and less ambiguous is the meaning of the term. For example, most of the terms characterized by extra- and interdomenial polysemy can be confused with their semantic counterparts (*concept, reproducere, spațiu, șablon*, etc.), while the ultra-specialized monosemantic terms, such as: *andruc, biguire, calandrare, coligat, galvanoglifie, leucografie, litocromie, oleofilizare, postfață, punct de raster*, etc., cannot be confused with any other terms.

These ultra-specialized terms can only be understood through the definitions in specialized dictionaries. The editorial-polygraphic text, apparently accessible, due to many words from the common language, is still difficult to decode without the help of an explanatory dictionary. In the fragments presented above we notice the preponderance of the non-specialized lexicon to the detriment of the specialized one. However, for an ordinary reader, the text is quite difficult to understand, to decode, keeping a substantial part of restrictive code, intended for the specialized reader.

Thus, the examples excerpted from the corpus mentioned above are edifying to illustrate the fixed character of the editorial-polygraphic statements, in which certain patterns are followed, such as descriptions of some polygraphic processes, or of some typographic tools, etc.

In conclusion, we can vehemently state that the contextual disambiguation of editorial-polygraphic terminology can be achieved by avoiding polysemantic terms, insisting on monosemantic and monoreferential terms. Polysemy increases the ambiguity of the terms. However, this goal is difficult to achieve, given that a large part of EP terms have a polysemantic character, due to the resemanticization (terminologization) or redomenialization (reterminologization) of the terms. New terminological creations that designate unique concepts, existing only in a certain field, are called *neonyms*. Terminological creations arising from the resemanticization of a lexeme, whether from the common lexicon (terminology), or from the specialized lexicon of another field (reterminologization), are called *neosemants*.

Selecting only monosemantic, or ultra-specialized, i.e. neonym terms, would ideally be possible, but very restricted by volume: a sentence, a paragraph, but not a text, because some concepts have no other representations than those represented by polysemantic terms. Avoiding polysemantic terms would mean the impossibility of efficiently describing editorial-polygraphic phenomena and processes.

Thus, the text has the role of a tool for disambiguation of editorial-polygraphic terminology, with the help of which the receiver can distinguish the text message generated by the sender of the text, and the decoding of the message is done with the help of dictionaries or other specialized texts.

References

- Breaking News / Românii vor scoate organe la imprimanta 3D. (2017, 4 noiembrie). In *Timpul.md*. <https://www.timpul.md/articol/breaking-news---romanii-vor-scoate-organe-la-imprimanta-3d-123131.html>.
- Broșător. (f.d.). <https://999.md/ro/28219250>.
- Buruiană, M. et al. (2015). *Abecedar. Știința-Prut internațional*.
- Caldararu, E. *Povestea cărții de povești*. <http://www.copilasul.com/povesti-povestiri/POVESTEA-CARTII-DE-POVESTI-de-Emilia-Caldararu--BM-COM.php>.
- Caragiale, I. L. (1892). *Norocul culegătorului*. https://www.titudorancea.com/z/ion_luca_caragiale_norocul_culegatorului.htm
- Codul muncii. <https://www.cnpm.md>.
- Colța, O. (2012, 3 mai). *Cartea, un dar pe care o poți deschide iar și iar*. In *Ziarul de Gardă*. <https://www.zdg.md/editia-print/social/cartea-un-dar-pe-care-il-poti-deschide-iar-si-iar>.
- Dicționar de termeni tipografici. (f.d.). <https://www.imprint.md/blog/36.html>.
- Dumitrof, A. (2002, 22 martie). *Nuvela*. <http://www.poezie.ro/index.php/poetry/15994/Nuvela>.
- HP LaserJet P2015 Series. (2011). *Ghidul utilizatorului*.
- Manole, I. (2014). *Erată la viața unui tipograf*. Editura Ecou Transilvan.
- Noran, S., Vintilescu, R., Tanase, V. (1988). *Micul tipograf*. In *Cutezători*. <http://www.revistacutezatorii.blogspot.com/2010/2012/micul-tipograf.html>.
- Prima carte tipărită în limba română. (2015, 30 ianuarie). <https://radiochisinau.md/prima-carte-tiparita-in-limba-romana-19312>.
- Scobioală, V., Lisnic, V. (2008). *Procese editoriale. Anexe. Partea I-a*. Universitatea Tehnică a Moldovei.
- Scobioală, V., Lisnic, V. (2010). *Tehnologii poligrafice – flexografia. Partea I. Note de curs*. Universitatea Tehnică a Moldovei.
- Ungureanu V. (2008). Dezambiguizarea contextuală a sinonimelor. *Filologia modernă*, 347.